

THE ISSUE OF FORMING PROFESSIONAL COMPETITIVE QUALITIES IN YOUNG GENERATION

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Abstract. The article discusses the interpretation of the formation of professional competitive qualities in young generation in terms of social sciences and humanities. Content analysis will be conducted to ensure employment in the labor market by directing young people to professional activities and strengthening their competitiveness.

Key words: professional competitive qualities, competitiveness, need and motivation, knowledge and skills, level of development, professional orientation.

Аннотация. Мақолада, ижтимоий-гуманитар фанлар нуқтаи назаридан, ёш авлодда касбий кўникмаларни шакллантириш масалалари ўрганилган. Ёшларни касбий фаолиятга йўналтириш ва уларнинг рақобатбардошлигини кучайтириш орқали меҳнат бозорида бандликни таъминлаш юзасидан контент-таҳлил ўтказилган.

Калит сўзлар: профессионал рақобатбардошлик сифатлари, рақобатбардошлик, эҳтиёж ва мотивация, билим ва кўникмалар, ривожланиш даражаси, касбий йўналиш.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается интерпретация формирования профессиональных конкурентоспособных качеств у молодого поколения с точки зрения социальных и гуманитарных наук. Контент-анализ будет проводиться для обеспечения занятости на рынке труда путем направления молодежи на профессиональную деятельность и усиления ее конкурентоспособности.

Ключевые слова: профессиональные конкурентные качества, конкурентоспособность, потребность и мотивация, знания и умения, уровень развития, профессиональная направленность.

The study of young generation as the future of our country, the agents of social development, and change; therefore, the study of issues related to them is of great importance in New Uzbekistan. It was noted that “Education and upbringing the younger generation, accelerating the pace of the scientific and technological development, improving the life of the country are the basis for the development of society,

in addition to deal successfully with the critical issues in the 21st century”¹. Since science and education are the most important aspects of development; the application of theory in practice, is likely to result in significant modifications from quantitative to qualitative indicators in social, economic, cultural and political levels of society². The COVID-19 pandemic in the world has caused significant changes in the

¹ Isakova Z.R. National and universal values are an important factor in the spiritual maturity of young people. The role and importance of philosophy in the implementation of the Actions' Strategy on the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017–2021. Materials of the Republican scientific-theoretical conference. - Fergana: FarSU, 2019. - P. 78-80.

² Samarov R. Science and education in the strategy of national development: political and philosophical aspects // Philosophy and law. 2017/2 (№10). - P. 7 - 10.

life of society, which, in turn, has had an impact on the formation of competitive qualities of young people. As an example, we can cite the theoretical conclusions put forward as a result of research conducted in this regard. In the UK, for example, the results of a twenty-year sociological survey conducted by the Competitiveness Scorecard for Northern Ireland using a competitive methodology as part of a fundamental research project using the Competitiveness Methodology are particularly noteworthy. It created a competitiveness map, involved more than 100,000 respondents, and conducted a three-stage study involving various theoretical data. In the first stage, the living standards and welfare of the population, in the second stage, economic and social factors affecting the living standards of the entire population, in the third stage, more than 150 indicators of competitiveness in terms of environmental status were identified³. According to the study, the introduction of the COVID-19 pandemic had the greatest impact on the creation of a competitive rating map. In particular, there have been some difficulties in taking into account the vulnerable and poor part of the pre-existing population. It was also noted that long-term perceptions of where and to whom social policies should be directed to provide maximum support to businesses and individuals during the pandemic, and recovery phases have led to a change. The main goal of the policy is to save people's lives, prevent over-exertion of the health care system and maintain economic and social activity as much as possible. Recommendations have been made to prevent the decline in youth competitiveness, to maintain positive indicators of well-being, technological infrastructure and environmental sustainability, to provide high-quality of education to young people, to help them acquire knowledge and skills, and to further support the population, including the youth. Proposals and recommendations have been made to strengthen social policy, make full use of the opportunities of the digital and green economy, develop competitive skills in the youth to ensure the social development, as well as to increase the youth income and their living stand-

ards, bring international experts to the attention of the youth⁴. It is time to make important decisions on the implementation of research results, which are widely recognized by international experts. This makes it even more relevant to study the social factors that strongly influence the formation of competitive qualities of young people entering the labor market for the first time in modern times.

It is known that research on competition and competitiveness has been carried out within the boundaries of economics, sociology, management, psychology and pedagogy and other disciplines. However, these terms are widely and actively used in economic and production relations. In our opinion, little attention is paid to the sociological, psychological, managerial and pedagogical aspects of competition and competitiveness.

This is because the sociological peculiarity of the concept of “competition” is that it is understood “not as a competition between unrelated and independent participants, but as a social movement aimed at other market participants”⁵. Accordingly, a distinctive feature of competitive activity is to achieve higher results than the competitor.

According to H. White, when considering competition from a sociological point of view, it is necessary to assess its basic conditions. These are:

- formation of behavioral strategies, taking into account each other's actions;
- taking into account the interdependence of market participants;
- to take into account the existence of a wide exchange of information between market participants⁶.

In the context of sociological interpretation, in the process of competition, agents enter into social relations and help to ensure the success of the competitive process, as well as influence the acquisition of knowledge and professional skills by the individual and the individual's readiness for such relationships. Researcher D.N. Gerasimchuk writes that the most important element of an effective competition strategy is social networks. “If an individual is strongly supported in the

³ Richard Johnston, Gillian McCausland & Karen Bonner. The Competitiveness Scorecard for Northern Ireland. A framework for measuring economic, social and environmental progress. / Ulster University Economic Policy Centre, 2020. – P. 195.

⁴ Ibid – P. 120-125.

⁵ Radaev V.V. What is competition? // Economic sociology. 2003. - P. 16–25. - https://ecsoc.hse.ru/da-ta/2011/12/08/1208204948/ecsoc_t4_n2.pdf#page=16.

⁶ White H. C. Markets from Networks: Socioeconomic Models of Production. - Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2002. - P. 38–79.

form of multiple social connections and participation in social networks, one will be able to access information from a variety of sources and, as a result, become more competitive⁷. In doing so, the researcher focuses on the information factor in increasing competitiveness. It should be highlighted that the information process has a strong impact on the development trend, as well as accelerating the pace of processes. In this regard, Professor R. Samarov writes that today young people use various methods and means of communication to acquire the latest information. However, efforts are being made to perpetuate stereotypes simultaneously such as, “American World View”, “Russian World View”, “China World View”⁸, which, in turn, indicates the need to pay attention to the accuracy of information used in the formation of competitive qualities in young people.

Successful agents in the labor market are individuals with certain soft and hard skills and social capital. Investing in human and social capital is the most beneficial strategy to increase personal competitiveness. In this regard, Professor M. Bekmurodov writes that “If a person invested from the age of 3 to 22; later in life 19-22 times more profitability can be achieved, while this figure gives only 4 times profit in Uzbekistan”⁹. This means that not only the young professionals themselves, but the whole society and the state are to get the benefit from the formation of competitive qualities in young people. Therefore, Professor T.U. Abdullaev, considering the complexity of the process of formation of competitive qualities of young people, said: “Therefore, one of the tasks of science is to increase the knowledge and cognitive abilities of young people along with the life experience”¹⁰. At the same time, he approached the issue in a functional way, and in our opinion, it is expedient to take into account the role of social factors

in this process. According to G.Z. Yefimova, who conducted a research on the formation of competitive qualities in young people, the level of competitiveness is directly related to social factors such as “social class”, “general satisfaction with life”, “respect for health”, “striving for a healthy lifestyle”. Particularly, education plays an important role in this¹¹. Hence, factors such as investing in education, health, and an individual’s quality of life are also of strategic importance to ensure a high level of competitiveness.

As per to I.V. Terelyanskaya, “The competitiveness of young people in the labor market is determined by knowledge, skills and qualities of professional importance, high qualification, ability to quickly adapt to conditions and more effectively perform professional functions and roles”¹². L.V. Lvov and O.V. Perevozova consider competitiveness as an integral professional and personal qualities, consisting of a set of knowledge, activities, professional and personal components that meet the requirements of the labor market and allow to apply to the employer, reflecting the level of development of professional competence¹³. V.I. Shapovalov asserts that in the paradigm of innovative pedagogical management, the competitiveness of young people is a “socially oriented system of abilities, characteristics and qualities of the individual, which characterizes the potential for success (in education, professional and non-professional life). It is a factor that provides individual behavior, inner self-confidence, harmony with himself and the world around him in a dynamically changing environment”¹⁴.

In the narrow interpretation, competitiveness is often determined by young people’s compliance with the labor market requirements, which allow them to

⁷ Gerasimchuk D.N. Social capital as a factor of competition of subjects of the regional labor market. / Dis. ... cand. sociological Sciences. - Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk, 2015. - P. 50.

⁸ Samarov R. Mechanism of psychological security of information (methodical manual). - Tashkent: Universitet, 2015. - P. 18.

⁹ Bekmurodov M. Sociological basis of social development processes. / Current issues of modern sociology in an informed society. Materials of the Republican scientific-practical conference. - Tashkent: National University of Uzbekistan, 2019. -P. 22-25.

¹⁰ Abdullaev T.U. The role of philosophy in the growth of youth activism. / The role and importance of philosophy in the implementation of the Actions’ Strategy on the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021. Materials of the Republican scientific-theoretical conference. - Fergana: FarSU, 2019. - P. 5-7.

¹¹ Yefimova G.Z. Competitiveness and competitiveness in the assessment of student youth. //Education and science. Vol. 19, No. 7. 2017 / The Education and Science Journal. Vol. 19, No. 7. 2017. -P. 97.

¹² Terelyanskaya I.V. Study of the competitiveness of university students as an integral characteristic of personality // Higher education today. 2012. No. 4. - P. 26–28.

¹³ Lvov L.V., Perevozova O.V. The content of the phenomenon of "competitiveness" in vocational education // Bulletin of the Chelyabinsk State Agroengineering Academy, 2014. V. 67/2. - P. 52–57.

¹⁴ Shapovalov V. I. Competitiveness of the individual in the paradigm of innovative pedagogical management // Yaroslav. ped. herald. - 2003. - No. 4. - P. 61–69.

apply for certain vacancies. However, some authors have highlighted the different aspects of personal and career competitiveness. They have indicated that personal competitiveness is often seen as a success in domestic and social life, while career competitiveness is seen as a professional achievement¹⁵. Although these two types of competition are used interchangeably, there are also scientific studies showing that these are different concepts¹⁶. In particular, scientific research has been conducted by W. Pavot and E. Diener as per the level of satisfaction of young people with their social life in order to take a worthy place in the labor market. Based on their theoretical approaches, they describe an individual's satisfaction with the enjoyment of life¹⁷.

M. Frijens argues that individuals try to generalize the quality of their lives through life satisfaction, which is influenced by many aspects of life¹⁸, while R. Veenhoven claims that social resources, ie economic well-being, social equality, social position as well as personal resources, family values and physiological condition, intellectual potential, empathy, problem-solving and other similar personal abilities are factors that determine life satisfaction¹⁹. Hence, it is also important to determine the level of life satisfaction among the factors influencing the formation of competitive qualities of young people.

Researcher E.A. Polishchuk pointed out the following as the main parameters of youth competitiveness:

- educational and professional level, intellectual and creative potential, covering the level and quality of vocational education, its suitability for the needs of the economy, professional skills, accumulated intellectual potential, creative attitude to work;

- professional mobility of young people, their ability and readiness to acquire new professional knowledge, improvement of their skills, search for a more attractive labor market, as well as in the national and international labor markets;

- level of health, the ability to withstand the modern rhythm and intensity of work, the ability to adapt physically and psychologically to rapid changes in working conditions;

- activity, initiative, responsibility, willingness to cooperate, teamwork, social and mental characteristics, etc²⁰.

Researcher V.I. Shapovalov, who approached the issue from a structural and functional point of view, suggests to distinguish the following components of competitiveness:

- 1) paradigmatic-prognostic (includes identification of personal prospects of competitive behavior, self-improvement, adaptation of behavior to the ideal model);

- 2) information-content which forms a complex of knowledge related to “self-awareness”, includes the definition of life strategies and tactics, decision-making;

- 3) operational activity which includes self-esteem, communicative and regulatory actions, knowledge, skills and competencies that determine success;

- 4) motivational-value which includes the value orientation of the individual, the desire for moral self-improvement, a positive attitude to various socially important activities, the need for self-expression, self-affirmation;

- 5) emotional-volitional which includes such qualities as responsibility, independence, initiative, self-confidence, empathy, self-control²¹.

Education, as a social institution, is the basis for the formation of the qualities of competitiveness of young people, as well as the systematic functioning of each sector of society and the dynamics of development. It is because young people need knowledge and information to create and introduce new technologies, to improve them, to diagnose them, to forecast them, to identify threats, risks and dangers to the industry in a timely manner, and to determine the methods. In this regard, D. Bell, considering the entry of mankind

¹⁵ Andreev V.I. Competitiveness. - Kazan: Center for Innovative Technologies, 2013. – P.356.

¹⁶ Reznik S.D. Who will teach a student to live? // Higher education in Russia. 2015. No. 1. - P. 146-152.

¹⁷ Pavot W., Diener E. Review of the Satisfaction with Life Scale. // Psychological Assessment, 1993. 5 (2). - P. 164-172.

¹⁸ Frijns M. Determinants of life satisfaction, Cross Regional Comparisons. Maastricht University. 2010. - P. 65.

¹⁹ Veenhoven R. Developments in satisfaction-research. Social Indicators Research, 37(1), 1996. - P. 1-46.

²⁰ Polishchuk E.A. Systematization of the components of the competitiveness of youth in the labor market // Collection of the 1st scientific conference: Days of Science KFU. V. I. Vernadsky. 2015. - P. 10-11.

²¹ Shapovalov V. I. Competitiveness of the individual in the paradigm of innovative pedagogical management // Yaroslav. ped.herald. - 2003. - No. 4. - P. 61–69.

into the information age as the most important sign of post-industrial society writes, “As we approach the end of the twentieth century, it is becoming increasingly clear that we are entering the information age. This means not only the development of previously existing methods of communication, but also the implementation of new principles of social and technological organization. The new information age is not based on mechanical technology, but on “intellectual technology”. In this regard, D. Bell emphasizes the role of individual theoretical knowledge, the growing importance of the class of knowledge carriers, which has become the dominant group in the social structure of society”²². In our view, the institutional importance of knowledge will not diminish in any period and in the future.

The number of researchers have also commented on the factors influencing the formation of competitive qualities in young people. For instance, researcher E.O. Kadirov writes that academic lyceums and vocational schools, as well as technical schools play an important role in shaping the competitive qualities of young people, which “allows young people to concentrate on a task, develop the ability to use different forms of logical thinking. The intellectual activity of this group of young people tends to deepen, generalize and abstract, explain the causes of events, draw reasonable conclusions, take a critical approach to the views of others”²³. As for the distinctive features, we can only say that they are characterized by mobility, activity, aspiration to innovation. Young people evaluate what is happening now and in the past from the perspective of the future²⁴.

According to R. Samarov, if we consider that “the problem of the institute in the past (last century) is to ensure the universality of education (equality

for all), today the problem of the institute of education is to ensure the quality of education for all (quality education for all), which, in turn, highlighted the next task of the Institute of Education, i.e. the issue of providing quality education to each student (individual) by type and specialty of education”²⁵. Professor R.S Samarov pointed out the need for a functional approach to education and the formation of competitive qualities of young people. Especially, during the COVID-19 pandemic in the world, the globalized online education system has shown that there is a high level of need and demand for sociological research to find solutions to a number of issues facing the Institute of Education. In this regard, a number of practical experimental studies have been conducted by sociologists, psychologists, economists and researchers from developed countries (USA, Canada, UK and etc), in which: 1) to determine the socio-psychological impact of COVID-19 on students; 2) development of profiles for the classification of psychological expectations of students during a pandemic; 3) Socio-demographic potential, lifestyle issues and awareness of young people about the risk factors of COVID-19, the impact of these processes on the competitive qualities of young people in the context of a contextual approach²⁶. It should be noted that unfortunately, we have not yet conducted the systematic research in this regard.

According to N.K. Zaretdinova, today the following trends are observed in the labor market of the republic: 1) increase in the number of university graduates; 2) a significant decrease in the number of graduates of vocational education institutions; 3) many young people prefer to get a higher education, but in the future will not work in their specialty, and even occupy a position that does not require a higher educa-

²² Bell. E. The coming post-industrial society. Experience of social forecasting. - M.: 2004. - P. 9.

²³ Kadirov E.O. Issues of raising the legal and political culture of youth (on the example of academic lyceums and professional colleges). Doctor of Science (DSc) dis. abstracts. - Tashkent, 2019. – 63 p.

²⁴ Melikova M.N. Historical consciousness of the youth of Uzbekistan (socio-philosophical analysis). Author's abstract of the dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in philosophy. - Samarkand, 2019. - P. 14.

²⁵ Samarov R.S. Structural and functional aspects of determining the content of education (on the example of person-centered education) // *Sovremennoe obrazovanie* 2015, No12. - 9-14 p.

²⁶ Germani A, Buratta L, Delvecchio E, Mazzeschi C. Emerging adults and COVID-19: The role of individualism-collectivism on perceived risks and psychological maladjustment. *IJERPH*. 2020; 17: 3497–15. pmid:32429536; Aristovnik A, Keržič D, Ravšelj D, Tomažević N, Umek L. Impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on life of higher education students: A global perspective. *preprints.org*. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202008.0246.v2>; Huckins JF, daSilva AW, Wang W, Hedlund E, Rogers C, Nepal SK, et al. Mental health and behavior of college students during the early phases of the COVID-19 pandemic: Longitudinal smartphone and ecological momentary assessment study. *J Med Internet Res*. 2020;22: e20185. pmid:32519963; Zimmermann M, Bledsoe C, Papa A. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on college students' mental health: A longitudinal examination of risk and protective factors. *psyarxiv.com*. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/2y7hu>.

tion²⁷. It is obvious that the issue of forming the qualities of professional competitiveness among the youth of our country is becoming more urgent.

The Center for Development Strategy points that a strong legal framework has been created in our country to protect the rights and interests of young people, to create the necessary conditions and opportunities for them, and this system is being improved in line with modern requirements. In particular, up until, the parliament has adopted more than 40 laws on youth and ratified more than 30 international legal instruments²⁸. This, in turn, creates the basis for quality education, professional development and competitive growth of young people, as well as comprehensive support for the younger generation, educating them to be spiritually mature, physically healthy, patriotic and selfless, to protect their rights and interests. While motivating our young people have been as productive as possible, it is also instilling in them a sense of confidence toward their future. This allows us to look at the youth, which is recognized as not as a “problem”, but as a major force in the development of the country, a strategic resource of the state. As a result, today the issue of educating assertive, open-minded, and competitive young people is becoming a matter of great urgency. In order to do this effectively, it is important to establish a cooperation in society. As researcher Howard Beverley points out, “cooperation of youth is a powerful intervention that can be undertaken to support the physical, personal, social and emotional development of young people²⁹”.

In conclusion, in the development of professional competitiveness of young people, it is crucial to point out the following:

- The qualities of professional competitiveness of young people are primarily related to the family factor, in which career choice is made primarily on the basis of life examples of family members, parents and close relatives;

- Achieving quality indicators at all stages of education;

- Orientation of young people in secondary and high schools to a profession and in certain specialties;

- Support of talented and gifted youth, encouragement of their socially significant initiatives;

- Ensuring employment in the labor market by directing young people to professional activities and strengthening their competitiveness;

- Ensuring the harmony of theory and practice in the development of professional competitiveness of young people in higher education institutions;

- The quality of competitiveness depends on the effective reforms in education, which, in turn, contributes to the increase of a competitive professional youth;

- Analysis of socio-psychological factors affecting the competitiveness of young people shows that young people need to constantly study, strive for innovation, focus on developing skills to be able to introduce innovative technologies in their professional activities. For this purpose, it is necessary to include in the curricula of the higher education system courses “Sociology of “Competition”, “Psychology of Competition”, “Strategy and Tactics of Competition”, a module “Methodological basis for the formation of competitive skills” in the system of training and re-training.

²⁷ Zaretdinova N.K. Sociometric regulation of career choice of young people in the family (on the example of the Republic of Karakalpakstan). Author's abstract of the dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in sociology. - Tashkent, 2020. - 50 p.

²⁸ “Development Strategy” Center. <https://strategy.uz/index.php?news=615>

²⁹ Howard Beverley. Youth work's contribution to provision for young people with mental health issues, in the borough of bury, greater manchester. Masters thesis, University of Huddersfield, 2018. - P.13.